

Information Technology and Knowledge Enabling Factors: an Empirical Investigation Using Confirmatory Factor Analysis.

Author Details:

Dr. Firas M. Alkhaldi, Amman Arab University, Amman , Jordan

Abstract

It has been argued by my philosophers and practitioners that information systems/technology plays an imperative role in knowledge creation, yet none has devolve deeply into what attribute and capabilities should IT possess to create a dimensional shift to move from information to knowledge context. This paper capitalized on this gap to provide the needed perspective to comprehend the nature of IT support. A detailed analysis has been adopted by focusing on IT capabilities to the knowledge enabling factors. A robust methodology and critical evaluative criteria was adopted. A confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modelling strategy was selected as the analysis tool to achieve the research objectives.

Key words: *Information technology, knowledge creation, knowledge enabling factors, confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation modelling.*

Introduction

The recent advancement in information technology, such as the web technology exemplified as the networking technology (intranet, extranet and the internet), coupled with the increasing interest of knowledge creation, and has widened the organizational interest in the subject of knowledge management (Camisón and Forés 2011; Dufva, M and Ahlqvist, 2015). Information technology has led many organizations to expect a new world of leverage knowledge (Nor Aziatialet. Al. 2013; Tully et.al, 2013). However, organizations in their knowledge management initiatives focused their attention on the trivia of information technology tools by classifying knowledge as static and syntactic, ignoring the human aspects of how individuals or communities in the organization go about creating and sharing knowledge. It is wrong to view knowledge as unproblematic, predefined and pre-packaged, while disregarding the human dimension of knowledge creation in the organizations (Davenport and Prusak, 1998). This viewing of knowledge by the organization has worked against the generation of multiple and contradictory viewpoints necessary to meet the challenge created by the ever changing business environment which, in return, has hampered the organizational learning abilities (Malhotra, 1997). He considers that knowledge management solutions that are demarcated by memorisation of “best practise” which are embedded in the information technology can only be efficient if the situation its dealing with is liner, static and predictable, given that the business environment is stable or incrementally changing. Malhotra’s views with regard to the knowledge management solutions are based on “best practice” and in line with McDermott, (1999) where the later considers the result of “best practice”

intuitive as a “expensive useless information junk yard”. This view is also consistent with those of Davenport and Prusak, (1998, p. 7) when they describe this process as “*de-knowldging*”, where knowledge is sent back from its final form as a knowledge to information and then data, where data is an abstract with no meaning. Davenport and Prusak mention an example of how one of the Anderson consulting knowledge managers, view their own knowledge repository, “ *we’ve got so much knowledge (not to mention data and information) in our knowledge Xchange repository that our consultant can no longer make sense of it. For many of them it has become data*” (Davenport and Prusak, 1998, p.7). In other words, creating knowledge management systems with no regard to the human context in which knowledge is created, the characteristics of knowledge and without understanding the knowledge needed, the levels of details required by organizational members. It can be seen as “robbing” knowledge of its life and, in return, these systems would do little to lever knowledge. In order for knowledge management initiatives, systems and programs to succeed, Malhotra (1997) suggested Hegelian inquiry systems (Hegelian systems are referred to the philosopher Hegel, where his view of an inquiry systems are based on a synthesis of multiple completely antithetical representations that are characterised by intense conflict because of the contrary underlying assumptions) for an IT enabled knowledge management since it is better situated for an ever-changing environment coupled with devoted and serious recognition of the nature of knowledge creation processes. He suggested that for IT enabled knowledge management to succeed more attention should be paid to the nature of knowledge creation processes, where it is characterised as dynamic and evolving, multiple dimensions: tacit and explicit, subjective, interpretative,

meaning making bases and constructive. As such, Tutly et. al. (2013) suggested that a clear difference should be made between information and knowledge since sharing knowledge requires different set of concepts and tools, and knowledge management systems should embark on the characteristics of knowledge. The views of McDermott (1999) and Malhotra (1997) are consistent with Wilmott (1998) who sees knowledge management more as a way of signalling the key importance of how knowledge is created, valued and shared within the organizations rather than a technique for encountering the demands or opportunities of the information age. In summary, knowledge management is a set of organizational processes that govern the process of creating, disseminating and leveraging knowledge in the organization to attain its end objectives.

Many researcher such as Kruger et. Al. 2010, indicated in a way that the for knowledge management to succeed it has to take into consideration two things. First, more attention should be given to the context in which knowledge is created and shared; "The Human Act" rather than the outcome of the process. Secondly, more attention should be paid to the knowledge characteristics, where tacit knowledge, the crucial part of knowledge, is in the human's head and should be nurtured rather than managed. Information technology that aids and enables knowledge management should be looked at as the medium for portraying, incorporating and deploying knowledge to promote collaboration across different functions and attitudes in the organization.

Organizational knowledge creation

Many researchers have looked at two dimensions of knowledge: explicit and tacit (Kogut and Zander, 1996; Nelson and Winter, 1982; Polanyi, 1966). Explicit knowledge is easy to define, capture and transfer in different formats, whereas tacit knowledge is difficult to codify and transfer, because it is deeply rooted in individual minds and individuals often cannot easily articulate their knowledge bases. Drawing on Michael Polanyi's (1966) distinction between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge, an enticing knowledge creation model from Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), Nonaka et.al, 200A, 2000b they viewed tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge as separate but mutually complementary entities. Their model shows that the basis of organizational knowledge creation is in the conversion of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge and vice versa and organizational knowledge is created based on the interaction and conversion between the two dimensions of knowledge (tacit and explicit) in a spiral manner. A process model of knowledge creation

develops on the critical presupposition that individual knowledge is created and enlarged by means of a social interaction between tacit and explicit knowledge. This interaction is called knowledge conversion. The interaction between the two main dimensions of knowledge allows positing four different modes of knowledge conversion. According to and Nonaka and Takeuchi (199, 1996), the knowledge creation process takes place through four modes of knowledge conversion.

The conversion process can be from tacit to tacit (socialization) leading to the creation of sympathized knowledge, tacit to explicit (externalization) that leads to the creation of conceptual knowledge, explicit to explicit (combination) directing to the creation of systemic knowledge and explicit to tacit (internalization) that leads to the creation of operational knowledge. It is rather important to indicate that the conversion does not occur within individuals but between individuals within an organization (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995).

Enabling factors of knowledge creation

In order for knowledge creation in the organization to be sustained a conducive environment is required. Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) identified five enabling conditions. Organizational intention can be exemplified by the organizational vision and mission statement, which guides workable activities. Autonomy is the degree of freedom granted to individuals in the organization, which promotes self-motivation and leads to the generation of new ideas. Fluctuation and creative chaos is the ease of making changes that simulate the interaction between the organization and the external environment. It is the tension between the actual performance of the organization and the desired future expressed through a clear and unambiguous vision, which is often referred to as the vision led company (Kanter et al., 1992). The existence of redundancy offers an overlapping knowledge within the organization and between its members, and promoting collaboration (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Requisite verity prevents information overloading and identifies the subject matter experts.

Information technology and knowledge enabling factors

A number of studies in organizational science have recognized the role and the importance of information technology in contributing to organizational knowledge creation and sharing (Kruger, 2010; Johnson, 2000; Choo, 1998) . This study proposes a different methodology where information technology could play a

significant role in supporting the construction and conversion of knowledge both tacit and explicit in an indirect way. This indirect way can be realized through introducing information technology to support knowledge enabling factors. Based on the above discussion about the enabling factors of knowledge creation, it can be argued that a number of factors are grouped together to form knowledge creation enabling factors (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). These factors can be classified under two categories: first, key factor enablers and secondly, attributes of the key factor enablers. The key factor enablers are intention, autonomy, redundancy, fluctuation and requisite variety. The attributes of the key factors enablers are transferability and memory an attribute of redundancy. Accessibility is an attribute of requisite variety.

Autonomy refers to a higher degree of freedom provided to individuals on their own or in teams within the organization. Autonomy should increase the possibilities of the individual to motivate him or herself and should work as a driver for the organization's members to generate new and original ideas. According to Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), autonomy is an important condition for promoting the knowledge spiral. They considered that, as far as circumstances permit, all the organization's members should be allowed to act autonomously. Information technology can play a significant role in promoting and supporting autonomy either in a direct or indirect way. Direct support comes from the fact that individuals can perform tasks and work on their own whenever the requirements needed to do so are available to them. An indirect support of information technology to increase the level of independence of individuals is by creating an extra horizon to experiment and try to solve a problem, with virtually no cost to the organization.

Redundancy in context of this study means the existence of information that goes beyond the immediate operational requirements of the organization's members (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Redundancy can be considered as an intentional overloading and overlapping of information between groups that promotes cross-functional collaboration (Scott, 2000). Sharing redundant information within the organization will encourage individuals to share their own tacit knowledge. Redundancy allows the organization's members to sense what others are trying to articulate and promote cross-functional collaboration which, in return, accelerates the knowledge creation process. Information technology, such as intranet, GroupWare and web

technology, offers the organization's members wide access to organizational information.

Information technology is deemed to play a significant role in providing the required redundancy. Memory as an attribute of redundancy is considered in this study, individuals are relying heavily on their memory when trying to solve a problem, or to bring up information of a similar case or piecing up relevant knowledge to form a potential solution.

Fluctuation/creative chaos in a constantly changing business environment, an organization that does not react quickly to changes, where information is constantly moving and changing rapidly, will be left behind and eventually dies. An organization should adopt an open posture towards any environmental change in order to improve its ability to create and capture new knowledge. The speed, flexibility and ease of making changes given to organizations by information technology such as the web technology will help an organization to react quickly and update its information with virtually no cost.

Requisite variety in the context of knowledge creation means preventing information overload and finding the subject matter expert. Information technology is viewed today as an information pull technology rather than an information push, which is in favour of the organization's members who are looking for who owns what information. Accessibility is an attribute of requisite variety; it refers to the ability to access relevant information. It is considered an essential trait in enabling people to make and create augmentation of knowledge; unless people have access to the information when they need it, it seems impossible for them to create new knowledge. Individuals use past information as a ladder or a stepping-stone in their drive to create new knowledge at a higher level (Khalil, 1996). Information technology tools can be used to increase accessibility

Intention is symbolised by the organization's mission statement that endures workable activities. The organization's vision and operational standards can also exemplify intention. Intention is deemed to be a significant factor which is transmitted via formal channels from the top management to the organizational members. An example of intention is when the leadership convey their vision regarding what type of knowledge should be developed. Comparing the type of support that IT can provide for intention with the previously mentioned knowledge enabling factors, the support here can be seen as static while the support of other factors is dynamic and, hence, this factor was seen

to be not appropriate to be included in the proposed model.

Research model development and hypotheses generation

Based on the theoretical development in the previous sections, a research model that relates information

H1: There is a direct positive relationship between IT and the time spent on organizational knowledge creation activities (Autonomy, Fluctuation, Redundancy and Requisite variety).

H1a: There is a direct positive relationship between ITs and Autonomy.

H1b: There is a direct positive relationship between IT and Fluctuation.

H1c: There is a direct positive relationship between IT and Redundancy.

H1d: There is a direct positive relationship between IT and Requisite variety.

technology support for knowledge creation enabling factors for knowledge transfer to the organizational knowledge creation activities is developed (See figure 1). The model proposes that information technology that provides support conducive for a knowledge environment will lead to positive participation knowledge activities.

Figure 1: Proposed research model of IT support OKC

Methodology

A positivistic approach was adopted to accomplish the objectives of this study. The research question was discussed, and the hypotheses were presented. A questionnaire was used as a method of data collection. The questionnaire was administrated largely to 155 middle managers in the banking sector, a 66% response rate was achieved and used in the calculation. The hypothesised models were analysed using CFA. The confirmatory modelling approach was carried out to examine the significant of the research model empirically. EQS 6.1 was used because of the many advantages that this program can offer (for more information about EQS 6.1, see mvsoft.com). Prior to running EQS, all constructs were tested for validity through factor analysis using principal components analysis with Varimax rotation (Byrne, 1994; Bentler, 1995; Field, 2001; Hair et. al., 2009).

Data Characteristics

The respondents’ average age was 38 years ranging from 23 to 55 and they have been at the present job for an average of 2.9 years but demonstrate an immense variation, ranging from 2 months to 12 years. The most frequent number of decision levels from the final approval was reported as 1 or 2 levels (63.7%) and the next frequent was 3 or 4 level (16.7%). Most of the respondents’ titles were managers 62.7%, and the next frequent position was senior managers 9.8%. The most frequent number of involvement in project innovation was 1-5 projects, which constitutes 35.3%. The next frequent number of involvement was more than a 15 projects, which represent 33.3%. The most frequent level of education was reported as postgraduate degree, 39.2% and the next frequent level of education was Bachelor’s degree at 32.4%. Approximately 72% were line managers, mostly in marketing and sales, and product development departments, and the remaining were engaged in accounting and finance, information technology and customer services.

Model Operationalization

This research selected the four enabling conditions where the belief is that IT can deliver the needed dynamic enhancement for the knowledge enabling factors. These dimensions are

- ❖ Information technology supporting redundancy (ITSR).
- ❖ Information technology supporting fluctuation (ITSF).
- ❖ Information technology supporting requisite variety (ITSRV).
- ❖ Information technology supporting work related autonomy (ITSA).

Items were developed mainly from adapted from a leading knowledge creation and IT literature where the items measure the perception of respondents based on their agreement or disagreement. Respondents were asked to rate each item on a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from ‘1=strongly disagree’ to ‘5=strongly agree’.

Information technology supports

All constructs as a the result of The explanatory factor analysis showed a one-factor solution, overall loading range ranging from 0.57 to 0.81, the average variance explained for all constructs was 0.55 for all contract. Reliability was measured using Cronbach’s alpha and it ranges from 0.57 to 0.96. See as in table 1

Table 1: Summary of factor analysis and the reliability test

Constructs	No. of items	Loadings	Variance Explained	Reliability value (α)
ITSR*	5	0.56-0.75	0.45	0.69
ITSF*	4	0.57-0.75	0.66	0.57
ITSRV*	5	0.57-0.73	0.64	0.64
ITSA*	3	0.68-0.81	0.42	0.58

* All constructs loaded on one factor

Information technology that supports knowledge Enabling factors (ITSKEFs)

After identifying in the previous section the underlying dimension of the variables and constructs (ITSR, ITSF, ITSRV and ITSA) that constitutes the information technology that supports knowledge enabling factors, and having confirmed the reliability and validity of these dimension through the use of EFA and CFA, the summated variables were then employed to form the ITSKEFs construct, where ITSKEFs were characterized as a latent variable. A model for ITSKEFs was constructed and CFA was executed to test for the overall goodness of fit for the proposed IKT construct. The results indicated good fit, as CFI equals 1.00, $X^2= 0.53$, $P= 0.47$ and RMSEA equals 0.00. All other indexes will not be calculated as this model represents a perfect fit. All coefficients are standardized and all were significant, ranging from 0.53 to 0.89. These all indicated that good discriminate and convergent validity was established for the ITSKEFs construct, uni-dimensionality was assured as GFI is greater than 0.90. Confirmatory analysis results for ITSKEFs construct can be seen in table 2, and figure 2.

Figure 1: Confirmatory factor analysis results for ITSKEFs

Data Analysis

Structural equation models:

This analysis was designed to test the relationship between the individual independent constructs ITSKEFs and their autonomous impacts on the dependent constructs, for simplicity, the proposed relationships between the independent and the dependent constructs can be viewed in the form of regression equations, as displayed below.

1. Independent construct ITSKEFs and KEF constructs, where these relationships are designed to test hypotheses H1a through H1d

- 1.1 ITSKEFs and R: $ITSKEFs f (R) \rightarrow ITSKEFs = \alpha R + \epsilon$
- 1.2 ITSKEFs and F: $ITSKEFs f (F) \rightarrow ITSKEFs = \alpha F + \epsilon$
- 1.3 ITSKEFs and RV: $ITSKEFs f (RV) \rightarrow ITSKEFs = \alpha RV + \epsilon$
- 1.4 ITSKEFs and A: $ITSKEFs f (A) \rightarrow ITSKEFs = \alpha A + \epsilon$

Measurement model: Hypothesis testing and analysis of the structural model

The measurement model fit show that the hypothesized model is a good fit and reliable based on the findings of the previous section, the measurement model will not be discussed here since the operationalization of ITSKEFs using CFA has already established. The analysis will proceed by discussing the findings of the structural model for all four models of ITSKEFs.

Table 2: Goodness of fit for the structural equation model of IT enabled Knowledge creation

AFM	IFM			Beta *
Hypothesized Model	$X^2;P$	GFI	RMSEA	R, 0.89
	, $X^2= 0.53, P= 0.47$	0.90	0.00	F, 0.67 RV, 0.75 A, 0.53

X^2 , Chi-square;; GFI, Goodness-of-fit index; RMSEA, Root-mean-square error of approximation; CFI, Comparative fit index. * all beta are accepted at 0.05 significate level, with a t value greater than 1.96

Discussion

The use of information technology that supports the knowledge creation enabling factors can help in storing, retrieving and accessing prior knowledge and, hence, helping organizations to create and share new knowledge. According to McCulloch (1965) as cited in Nonaka and Takeuchi, (1995, p. 81) “principle of redundancy of potential command” redundancy of information is a prerequisite to “realization”. Sharing redundant information facilitated by information technology can help an organization’s members to understand their role in the organization and, thus, control the direction of their thinking and action towards future knowledge creation activities. Information technology can enhance the requisite variety processed by an organization’s members by promising a fast access to the widest variety of applicable and essential information going through least possible steps, enabling individuals to associate information differently and amenably, and by identifying who owns the information, and where the information is located. While information technology supports autonomy by assuring that the necessary information needed by individuals is stored on his/her networking PC and, thus, can act when facing an enquiry or a decision. Information technology facilitate the supports and the ease of making changes to match the recurrent fluctuating of information that trigger a breakdown of routine and, thus, enable individuals to react quickly to new changes. This discussion implies that enabling factors of knowledge creation supported by

information technology will have reflective impacts on knowledge operation in an organisation.

Conclusion

It was argued in the context for this paper that IT with a specific capabilities and qualities that delivers the necessary and needed support to enhance and improve the enabling role of the knowledge creation factors. For IT infrastructure capabilities to support the knowledge enabling factors, IT should possess a number of capabilities and attributes such flexibility and integration, enabling speed and easiness of making changes to react to any new development and enabling communication, collaboration, and sharing of information. In this study four sub hypotheses were supported, where IT proof to play a significant role in supporting knowledge enabling conditions that lead to enhance and empower individuals on their time spent on knowledge activities.

References

Byrne, B. M. (1994). *Structural Equation Modeling with EQS and EQS/Windows*. SAGE Publication, London.

Bentler, P.M. (1995). *EQS Structural Equation Program Manual*. Encino, CA: Multivariate Software, Inc.

Camisón,C and Forés,B, Knowledge creation and absorptive capacity: The effect of intra-district shared competences, Scandinavian

Journal of Management, Volume 27, Issue 1, March 2011, Pages 66-86

Choo, Chun Wei, (1998). *The knowing organisation*. Oxford University Press.

Davenport, T., and Prusak, L. (1998). *The working knowledge*. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.

Dufva, M and Ahlqvist, T, Knowledge creation dynamics in foresight: A knowledge typology and exploratory method to analyse foresightworkshops, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Volume 94, May 2015, Pages 251-268

Field, A. (2001). *Discovering statistics using SPSS for Windows, advance techniques for the beginner*. Sage, London.

Johnson, W. H. (2000). *Technological innovation and knowledge creation: a study of the enabling conditions and processes of knowledge creation in collaborative R&D projects*. Unpublished Ph.D., York University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada.

Hair, J., Anderson, R, Tatham, R, and Black, W. , and Rolph E. Anderson (2009). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (7th Edition). Prentice-Hall International, New Jersey.

Khalil, O. (1996). Innovative work environment: the role of information technology and systems. *SAM Advance Management Journal*, 61(3): 32-39.

Kanter, R.M., Stein, B.A., & Jock, T.D. (1992). *The challenge of organizational change: how, companies experience it and leaders guide it*. New York: Free Press.

Kogut, B., and Zander, U., (1996). What firms do? Coordination, identity, and learning. *Organisational Science*, 7(5): 502-518.

Kruger, C.J. and Johnson, Roy D. Information management as an enabler of knowledge management maturity: A South African perspective, *International Journal of Information Management*, Volume 30, Issue 1, February 2010, Pages 57-67

Malhotra, Y., (1997), Knowledge management in inquiring organisations. *Proceedings of the 3rd American Conference on information systems*, Indianapolis, IN, August, 15-17: 293-295.

McDermott, R., (1999), Why information technology inspired but cannot deliver knowledge management. *California Management Review*, 41(4): 103-117.

Nonaka, I., and Takeuchi, H., (1995). *The Knowledge creating Company*. Oxford University Press.

Nonaka, I., (1994). A dynamic theory of organizational knowledge creation. *Organizational Science*, 5(1): 14-37.

Nonaka, I., and H. Takeuchi, (1996). A theory of organisational knowledge creation. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 11(7/8): 833-845.

Nonaka, I., Toyama, R. and Nagata, A. (2000b). A Firm as knowledge-creating entity: a new perspective on the theory of the firm. *Industrial Corporate Change*. 9(1): 1-20.

Nonaka, I., Toyama, R., and Konno, N., (2000A). SECI, *Ba* and leadership: a unified model of dynamic knowledge creation. *Long Range Planning*, 33(1): 5-34.

Nor Aziatia1, A.H. , Juhanab, S. and. Nor Hazanac, A. Knowledge Transfer Conceptualization and Scale Development in IT Outsourcing: The Initial Scale Validation International Conference on Innovation, Management and Technology Research, Malaysia, 22 – 23 September, 2013

Polanyi, M. (1966). *The tacit dimension*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.

Scott, J. E. (2000). Facilitating interorganizational learning with information technology. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 17 (2): 81 – 113.

Tully, Mary P. Asa Kettis, Höglund, Anna T. Mörlin, Claes Schwan, Ake , and Ljungberg, Christina. Transfer of data or re-creation of knowledge – Experiences of a shared electronic patient medical records system, *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, Volume 9, Issue 6, November–December 2013, Pages 965-974

Wilmott, H., (1998). Here today, gone tomorrow? In Stuart Rock (Ed.), *Knowledge Management*, Caspian Publishing Ltd., London. pp: 25-31.